

Table 1: Primary Studies Summaries

Title	Proposal	Summary	RQ	Ref.
A Deployment Model to Extend Ethically Aligned AI Implementation Method ECCOLA	methodology	Cyclical deployment model for ECCOLA with four core processes to prioritize ethical requirements, engage stakeholders, and align with agile development. Their Ethical Situational Picture tool visualizes requirement characteristics (e.g., stakeholder consensus, importance, prioritization changes) across the SDLC	2	[1]
From ethical AI frameworks to tools: a review of approaches	analysis	An ensemble approach combining methodologies, methods, tools, and frameworks to construct a comprehensive AI ethics infrastructure	3	[2]
A framework for assessing AI ethics with applications to cybersecurity	framework	A three-dimensional matrix for assessing AI ethics, with a focus on cybersecurity, that assesses the likelihood of ethical violations, the potential loss from such events, and the degree of conflict with ethical principles, helping to assess and mitigate ethical risks	1, 2	[3]
All that glitters is not gold: trustworthy and ethical AI principles	framework	Rees & Muller outline key AI ethics principles: robustness, lawfulness, fairness, responsibility, safety, diversity, and legality	2	[4]
A Rapid Review of Responsible AI frameworks: How to guide the development of ethical AI	analysis	Barletta et al. identified a structural imbalance in AI ethics frameworks through systematic review, highlighting their requirements-phase bias and calling for a plural integration to address lifecycle-wide ethical challenges	3	[5]
AI Ethics Impact Assessment based on Requirement Engineering	methodology	The authors propose a requirements engineering approach to systematically evaluate the ethical impacts of AI systems	2	[6]
Z-Inspection: A Process to Assess Trustworthy AI	process	Three-phase audit process (setup, assess, resolve) for AI trustworthiness, with systematic setup including context mapping, intellectual property considerations, and temporal risk assessment	2	[7]
Implementing AI Ethics: Making Sense of the Ethical Requirements	principles	—	1	[8]
How Do Software Companies Deal with Artificial Intelligence Ethics? A Gap Analysis	analysis	Vakkuri et al. analyses the AI ethics practices of 249 companies, revealing discrepancies between EU guidelines and industry implementation, particularly with regard to social well-being, human oversight, and comprehensive accountability frameworks	1	[9]
Governance of Ethical and Trustworthy AI Systems: Research Gaps in the ECCOLA Method	method	Agbese et al. evaluate ECCOLA through Singapore’s PDPC framework, finding comprehensive corporate governance coverage but identifying gaps in data and information governance that require methodological enhancement	2	[10]
Ethical Requirements Stack: A framework for implementing ethical requirements of AI in software engineering practices	framework	A tool designed to support the implementation of ethical AI requirements across organizational levels, organizing these requirements into four layers: Themes for strategic management, Epics for middle management, Features for operational management, and ethical user stories for teams, ensuring ethical considerations are embedded in standard software engineering practices	2, 3	[11]

Implementing AI Ethics in a Software Engineering Project-Based Learning Environment - The Case of WIMMA Lab	framework	Non-linear framework for AI ethics integration in PBL environments, utilizing student-generated documentation and cyclical tool application throughout project development	2	[12]
AI Ethics Principles in Practice: Perspectives of Designers and Developers	process	Sanderson et al. identified eight key AI ethics themes through CSIRO interviews, proposing dual operationalisation supports: organizational (policies, training) and developer-focused (design guidelines) for principled AI development	2	[13]
Beyond 100 Ethical Concerns in the Development of Robot-to-Robot Cooperation	framework	Analysis of ECCOLA in multi-robot systems (CACDAR project) identifies 12 ethical themes through expert workshops, extending the method with robot-specific concerns like value-based cooperation/confrontation	2	[14]
What Is the Cost of AI Ethics? Initial Conceptual Framework and Empirical Insights	framework	A three-phase ethical cost framework (investment, maintenance, revenue) bridging AI ethics and software quality principles	2	[15]
Ethics of AI: A Systematic Literature Review of Principles and Challenges	analysis	Khan et al. identified 21 core AI ethics principles (e.g., transparency, fairness) and seven implementation challenges, including principle vagueness and technical-practice conflicts	1	[16]
Ethics by Design for Intelligent and Sustainable Adaptive Systems	framework	An ethics-by-design framework using neural networks, where ethical rules are injected during training to guide AI decisions while avoiding discriminatory outcomes	2	[17]
Designing Up with Value-Sensitive Design: Building a Field Guide for Ethical ML Development	tool	Field guide that applies Value Sensitive Design to ML development, enabling practitioners to filter ethical mitigation strategies by development stage, problem type, and research field through an interactive web-based tool developed with expert input	2, 3	[18]
A participatory data-centric approach to AI Ethics by Design	process	A participatory, data-centric method emphasizing value-sensitive design (VSD) during AI development, with workshops and expert involvement in data preparation and value elicitation to address ethical concerns across the lifecycle	2	[19]
AI Ethics for Industry 5.0 – From Principles to Practice	framework	Ciobanu & Meșniță proposed a two-layer ethics framework for Industry 5.0 based on the VCIO model. The first layer supports pre-deployment training, principle definition, and risk testing. The second ensures ongoing ethical compliance through monitoring, evaluation, and updates	2, 3	[20]
Putting AI Ethics into Practice: The Hourglass Model of Organizational AI Governance	methodology	A three-layer hourglass model linking external ethical pressures, organizational strategy, and operational AI governance to align values and regulations with system implementation	2	[21]

How Do AI Ethics Principles Work? From Process to Product Point of View	analysis	Kemell et al. analysed how AI ethics principles can be integrated into product development. Using a fictional system, they identified key barriers such as weak implementation methods, overlapping principles, and limited accountability. They suggest framing ethics as risk and sustainability requirements to improve adoption	1, 3	[22]
The Different Faces of AI Ethics Across the World: A Principle-to-Practice Gap Analysis	analysis	A global gap analysis of 100 AI ethics principles and implementations, identifying structural barriers such as inadequate tooling, insufficient governance mechanisms, and lack of educational integration, with recommendations including EthicsOps, inclusive teams, regulatory enforcement, and cross-sectoral cooperation	3	[23]
Measuring Ethics in AI with AI: A Methodology and Dataset Construction	tool	—	-	[24]
Governance of Artificial Intelligence – A Framework Towards Ethical AI Applications	framework	Configurable governance framework integrating twelve operational domains and six design-specific variables to systematically assess, contextualize, and mitigate ethical risks in AI lifecycle management	2	[25]
Worldwide AI Ethics: a review of 200 guidelines and recommendations for AI governance	tool	A data-driven tool based on analysis of 200 global AI ethics guidelines, highlighting dominant principles, institutional actors, and gaps in diversity, transparency, and regulatory independence	1	[26]
ECCOLA — A method for implementing ethically aligned AI systems	method	Sprint-based card method composed of 21 cards across eight ethical themes (e.g., explainability, oversight, data quality, environmental impact), applied iteratively within agile development cycles to integrate, document, and verify ethical considerations across the AI system lifecycle	2, 3	[27]
The Importance of an Ethical Framework for Trust Calibration in AI	framework	A five-element framework for calibrating trust in AI systems, integrating failure models, occurrence probabilities, detectability, severity, and ethical impact across the software lifecycle to mitigate risk perceptions and enhance stakeholder confidence	2	[28]
The Role of Explainable AI in the Research Field of AI Ethics	analysis	Systematic literature mapping identifying key intersections between Explainable AI (XAI) and AI ethics, highlighting XAI's prominence in ethical discourse, the technical focus of empirical studies, and the notable research gap in its managerial and business implications	1	[29]
Towards a Roadmap on Software Engineering for Responsible AI	analysis	Structured roadmap for Responsible AI, detailing governance, process, and system-level practices to integrate ethical principles, ensure regulatory compliance, and implement RAI across development phases	3	[30]
Governance in Ethical, Trustworthy AI Systems: Extension of the ECCOLA Method for AI Ethics Governance Using GARP	method	An extension of the ECCOLA method integrating the GARP framework to address governance gaps, proposing enhancements to coverage of key principles like retention and disposal, and refining existing method cards for improved alignment with AI ethics practices	2	[31]

Fairness Score and process standardization: framework for fairness certification in artificial intelligence systems	framework	A structured framework for calculating fairness and bias indices in AI systems, comprising ten sequential steps for assessing protected attributes, calculating fairness scores, and certifying compliance with fairness standards	2	[32]
From AI ethics principles to data science practice: a reflection and a gap analysis based on recent frameworks and practical experience	analysis	Gap analysis, mapping HLEG AI ethics requirements to their practical applicability, identifying challenges in translating principles to operational practices, with a focus on ethics by design and the potential of Design for Values (DfV) for bridging the gap	3	[33]
Fairness in Design: A Tool for Guidance in Ethical Artificial Intelligence Design	framework	Card-based participatory framework for identifying and mitigating fairness risks in AI systems, integrating domain-specific stakeholder analysis, fairness principle application (group and individual), and iterative evaluation using structured metrics and Likert-scale assessments	2, 3	[34]
Putting AI ethics to work: are the tools fit for purpose?	analysis	A typology and comparative analysis of 169 AI impact assessment and audit tools, identifying trends such as the shift from data to models, stakeholder involvement discrepancies, and the predominance of internal tools with limited external oversight	2	[35]
Transparency and explainability of AI systems: From ethical guidelines to requirements	analysis	An empirical analysis of transparency and explainability practices in 16 organizations, identifying explainability component modeling and requirement templates as key methods, along with stakeholder-centered workshops and risk assessments to operationalise these principles	1, 3	[36]
Responsible AI Pattern Catalogue: A Collection of Best Practices for AI Governance and Engineering	process	Catalogue of RAI governance, process, and product standards, detailing 24 governance standards, process standards across the AI lifecycle (requirements, design, implementation, testing, operation), and product standards such as ethical verification tools, federated learning, and continuous ethical validation	2	[37]
Ethical Guidelines and Principles in the Context of Artificial Intelligence	analysis	—	1	[38]

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